

MSProfileR report

I. Data loading

- Number of spectra loaded: 344

II. Preprocessing

Trimming

Parameters

- Minimum mass: 2000 m/z
- Maximum mass: 20000 m/z

Results

Conformity test

Results

Criteria	Results
Number of empty spectra	0
Number of irregular spectra	0
Number of different lengths	0

Parameters

- Exclude empty spectra: Yes
- Exclude irregular spectra: Yes

Cleaning

Parameters

- Method used to transform intensity: Sqrt
- Method used to smooth intensity: Savitsky-Golay
- Half window size: 10
- Method used to remove baseline: SNIP
- Number of iterations: 100
- Method used to calibrate intensity: TIC

Results

Ctrl1_thorax_Aedes_aegypti [H1]

Quality control

Parameters

- Scale estimator: Q
- Method used for the identification of atypical spectra: RC
- Threshold: 5
- Include lower spectra: Yes

Results

- Number of typical spectra: 339/344

- Number of atypical spectra: 5/344
- Atypical spectra: 225: 08_thorax_Aedes_nigripes [A5], 289: 81_thorax_Aedes_pullatus [G10], 313: 65_thorax_Aedes_punctor [F5], 329: 69_thorax_Aedes_punctor [F10], 330: 69_thorax_Aedes_punctor [F11]

Averaging

Parameters

- Method: Mean

Results

- Number of spectra before merging: 339
- Number of spectra after merging: 86

III. Processing

Peak detection

Parameters

- Noise estimator method: MAD

- Half window size:
- SNR: 3

Results

Average number of peaks for SNR 3: 91.86 (sd: 10.04)

01_thorax_Aedes_nigripes [A1 A2 A3 A4]

Spectrum alignment

Parameters

- Method for reference peaks: MAD
- Minimum frequency of reference peaks: 0.7
- Tolerance for reference peaks: 0.002
- Warping method for alignment: Lowess

Results

- Number of reference peaks: 11

Peak binning

Parameters

- Method for binning: Strict
- Tolerance for reference binning: 0.002

Results

Number of peaks: 656

Peak filtering

Parameters

- Minimum frequency: 0.2

Results

Number of peaks: 157

Intensity matrix

Parameters

- Fill missing intensities using the aligned spectra: Yes

Results

